

TABLE 3—LOSS IN WEIGHT AND VALUES OF n AND k OF DIFFERENT STEEL SPECIMENS

Samples	Loss in weight W in $g\ m^{-2}$	Values of n	Values of k
<i>Mild steel (cold rolled)</i>			
Gas welded	96.6	1.08	1.8
Arc welded	98.9	1.08	1.7
Unwelded	89.4	1.08	1.6
<i>Mild steel (hot rolled)</i>			
Gas welded	85.5	1.07	1.70
Arc welded	88.9	1.07	1.66
Unwelded	77.7	1.07	1.55
<i>Stainless steel (AISI-304)</i>			
Gas welded	10.5	0.8	0.22
Arc welded	10.1	0.8	0.20
Unwelded	8.3	0.8	0.18

it, and also by the fact that all the chromium present is in the solid solution and the steel has a single phase structure. In case of mild steels for hot rolled, ϕ_{corr} is more anodic than cold rolled. These results are in agreement with the finding of the rate values from weight loss methods, i.e. the corrosion rate is in the order, cold rolled mild steel > hot rolled mild steel > stainless steel. From optical microscopic studies it is revealed that the preferential corrosion attack like pit formation takes place at the welded portions of the metal surface than at the base metal.

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Effect of Particle Size on the Kinetics of Thermal Decomposition of Limestone and Marble

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THE kinetic approach to the study of thermal decomposition of calcium carbonate is important because it is likely to provide basic information

about minerals, their structure etc. Whiting and Turner¹ noted the effect of grain size on the rate of decomposition of calcium carbonate. The observation of Hashimoto and Ito² reveals that the rate of thermal decomposition of calcite powder in CO₂ atmosphere is inversely proportional to the diameter of the particle. The present paper reports the effect of particle size on the kinetics of thermal decomposition of limestone and marble in air.

Experimental

The samples of limestone and marble samples were analysed following the standard procedure³.

Limestone and marble cubes (≈ 1 cm edge) with polished surfaces were prepared from cut samples. Surface area, volume and density of the cubes were determined. To study the effect of particle size on the rate of decomposition, particle sizes of between 853-422, 422-211, 211-124 and 89-64 μ were prepared from lumps of limestone and marble. Number of particles per g was calculated by the following formula presuming the particles as spheres,

$$n = \frac{6W}{\pi d^3 \rho}$$

where, n is number of particles per g of sample, W the weight of samples (g), d the average diameter of each particle (cm) and ρ the density of sample ($g\ cm^{-3}$). The surface area (S) was calculated by the following formula, $S = n\pi d^2$.

The weight loss of the samples was recorded in a thermobalance at suitable time intervals and in an atmosphere of CO₂ to prevent early decomposition of the sample.

Results and Discussion

Density and composition of the samples are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DENSITY AND COMPOSITION OF SAMPLES

Source	Limestone Jhinkpani (L ₁ , wt%)	Limestone Cuddapah (L ₂ , wt%)	Marble Makrana (M, wt%)
Loss on ignition	98.01	96.05	43.51
SiO ₂	10.65	23.90	0.81
Al ₂ O ₃	2.66	0.13	0.21
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.55	0.11	0.03
CaO	47.06	21.70	54.98
MgO	0.64	15.95	0.27
Density ($g\ cm^{-3}$)	2.717	2.704	2.719

It was felt that some modification of the equation, $(W/W_0)^{1/3} = 1 - k't$, derived by Britton *et al.*⁴ was necessary to explain the discrepancy observed by them. It was presumed that the decomposition of calcium carbonate occurs at the interface advancing from the surface of the particle to the interior. It was also considered that since it is a reversible

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reaction, the possibility of back-reaction cannot be overlooked and the amount of CO_2 formed at the interface should be equal to that diffusing through the decomposed CaO . The following equation was developed and reported in an earlier communication⁵,

$$\alpha = -(K_1 - K_2 P_0) \frac{K_2 d}{K_3} + (K_1 - K_2 P_0) \quad (1)$$

where, P_0 is pressure of CO_2 at the particle surface at a temperature t , d the depth of calcination from the particle surface, α the rate of weight-loss per unit area, i.e. overall rate of decomposition of calcium carbonate per unit area of decomposing surface, K_1 the rate constant of forward reaction per unit area which may be taken as constant, K_2 the rate constant of backward reaction per unit area, and K_3 the diffusion coefficient of CO_2 through the decomposed CaO layer.

According to equation (1), a plot of α vs d should be a straight line, the slope and intercept being $(K_1 - K_2 P_0) K_2 / K_3$ and $(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$, respectively. From the slope of the weight-loss vs time curves, total weight-loss per unit time at a particular depth (d) may be calculated. Table 2 shows the values of $(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$ for various limestone and marble cubes heated in air at different temperature⁸

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$ FOR VARIOUS LIMESTONE AND MARBLE CUBES HEATED IN AIR AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Sample no.	Temp. °C	$(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$
L ₁	750	7.56×10^{-4}
L ₂	750	4.29×10^{-4}
M	750	7.78×10^{-4}
L ₁	850	2.72×10^{-3}
L ₂	850	2.82×10^{-3}
M	850	2.6×10^{-3}

Table 3 shows the values of intercepts for four size fractions of limestone and marble heated in air.

The values of $(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$ for four size fractions of limestone and marble samples were significantly less than that obtained for limestone and marble cubes as can be seen from the comparison of data in Tables 2 and 3. It can also be noted that at a particular temperature and with the decrease in particle size, the value of $(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$ also decreases, which indicates that the values of P_0 for powders are much higher than that for cubes. This is what is expected as the diffusibility of CO_2 through pores between the particles should be less. Table 3 further shows that the value of P_0 increases with the decrease in particle size as the diffusibility of CO_2 decreases with the fineness of particles due to reduction in pore size. Thus the results agree with the model based on diffusion of products away from the interface coupled with chemical reaction.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF $(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$ FOR VARIOUS LIMESTONE AND MARBLE PARTICLES HEATED IN AIR AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Sample no.	Temp. °C	Av. diameter cm	$(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$
L ₄	650	0.063 8	0.7×10^{-5}
L ₃	650	0.031 6	0.4×10^{-5}
L ₂	650	0.016 7	1.71×10^{-6}
L ₁	650	0.007 6	0.88×10^{-6}
M	650	0.063 8	7.54×10^{-6}
M	650	0.031 6	4.01×10^{-6}
M	650	0.016 7	2.28×10^{-6}
M	650	0.007 6	1.23×10^{-6}
L ₄	850	0.063 8	5.12×10^{-4}
L ₃	850	0.031 6	2.53×10^{-4}
L ₂	850	0.016 7	1.38×10^{-4}
L ₁	850	0.007 6	0.73×10^{-4}
L ₄	850	0.063 8	5.07×10^{-4}
L ₃	850	0.031 6	2.30×10^{-4}
L ₂	850	0.016 7	1.72×10^{-4}
L ₁	850	0.007 6	0.87×10^{-4}
M	850	0.063 8	4.92×10^{-4}
M	850	0.031 6	2.66×10^{-4}
M	850	0.016 7	1.50×10^{-4}
M	850	0.007 6	0.69×10^{-4}
L ₄	950	0.063 8	2.25×10^{-3}
L ₃	950	0.031 6	1.12×10^{-3}
L ₂	950	0.016 7	0.50×10^{-3}
L ₁	950	0.007 6	0.23×10^{-3}
L ₄	950	0.063 8	3.3×10^{-3}
L ₃	950	0.031 6	1.32×10^{-3}
L ₂	950	0.016 7	6.54×10^{-4}
L ₁	950	0.007 6	3.36×10^{-4}
M	950	0.063 8	2.5×10^{-3}
M	950	0.031 6	1.13×10^{-3}
M	950	0.016 7	5.41×10^{-4}
M	950	0.007 6	3.42×10^{-4}

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